

OS Awards

European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source SW/HW Initiatives

D7.1 First/ Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable provides the first dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan for the OS Awards.EU project. It is the first of a series laying out the plan and reports on the first set of activities carried out until M06.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/ Acronym	Definition
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EOSA	European Open Source Academy
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OS	Open Source
FOSDEM	Free Open Source Software Developers' European Meeting
OSWeek	Open Source Week
OSPO	Open Source Programme Office
MS	Member State
WP	Work Package

About OS Awards.EU

OS Awards.EU is a 30-month initiative dedicated to establishing an European Open Source Academy and a prominent European Public Recognition Scheme for Open Source Software (OS SW) and Hardware (HW). By creating the annual European Open Source Awards, guided by the expert European Open Source Academy, the project will celebrate outstanding contributions and foster greater interest, integration, utilisation, and exploitation of OS assets across Europe.

Strategically leveraging the EU Open Source Week alongside key European events, the project will amplify the awards' profile and engage the community. The European OS Academy, in collaboration with the European Commission, will ensure award legitimacy and drive open source skills development. By intertwining recognition, legitimacy, and community engagement, OS Awards.EU aims to cultivate a comprehensive strategy that drives innovation, advances open source technologies, enhances EU competitiveness, and strengthens its open strategic autonomy.

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Executive summary

This document is the first in a series of three iterations of the OS Awards.EU dissemination, exploitation and communication plan. This document also serves as the communication plan of the European Open Source Academy (EOSA).

The portfolio of assets and results of OS Awards.EU are centred around three Key Exploitable Results to which all results of the project have been grouped under. This ensures that all results have dedicated communication and dissemination activities that are designed to support their exploitation or uptake. The KERs identified are:

- KER 1: European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework
- KER 2: Strategy for OS Skills Development
- KER 3: Thought-Leadership Outputs and Tools

For each KER, the preliminary exploitation plans have been identified – both individual and joint.

Stakeholders have also been identified with further detail on the relevant KERs and preferred channels for outreach. The stakeholders identified are policymakers, industry players, open source players, citizens, and investors and funding bodies.

The connection between project objectives, the newly identified KERs and respective communication, dissemination and exploitation plans have also been laid out. This ensures that the success of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plans ensure the success and achievement of the project objectives.

The document also outlines the available resources – both human, financial and competences that will be employed to carry out the plan.

The Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement Plan is divided into horizontal activities (activities that are carried out and tracked across the project lifetime) and campaigns (these have specific durations and targets to be reached by a deadline and are organised around a specific topic or goal). The horizontal activities include newsletters, social media posts, community building, publications, press visibility, among others. Campaigns, which have specific goals, are the following:

- Campaign 2: Academy Awareness & Participation
- Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion & Recruitment
- Campaign 4: OS Synergies

The channels to be utilised by the communications team have been outlined and include the website, social media and content repositories, events – both EOSA-organised and third-party events, email and newsletters, and press and media coverage.

A separate section on monitoring showcases the KPIs set and results to-date. Already, on the 6th month of the project, the horizontal activities and campaigns piloted to-date have achieved significant progress and validated the fitness of the plans laid out.

1 Introduction and scope

This deliverable series provides the plan for the dissemination, communication and exploitation of the OS Awards.EU project results and reports on the continuous monitoring of the implementation of this plan. This report provides an update that follows the preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plans outlined in the Description of Action (DoA). Among the main changes from the DoA are as follows:

- Majority of communication to external stakeholders will be done under the assumed identity of the “European Open Source Academy” instead of OS Awards.EU project. This means all channels will bear this identity.
- Campaigns have been reorganised while KPIs remain the mostly the same (with the exception for Twitter/X which has been replaced with Bluesky and Mastodon following a consortium decision).
- Overall, an update of the preliminary plans are given in the report.

This report is structured as such:

Section 1 identifies the **main assets** of the project, its Key Exploitable Results (KER) and groups various project results under the relevant KERs. This lightweight innovation management is necessary to be able to define the exploitation plans for each and design the appropriate dissemination activities to support them.

Section 2 outlines the **approach and methodology** in the implementation of the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities including the available resources to carry out the plan as well as the agreed approval procedure and guidelines.

Section 3 defines the **Communication and Dissemination strategy and implementation plan**. It defines the brand identities used, the channels and the structure of the implementation via horizontal activities and communication and dissemination campaigns.

Section 4 defines all the **key performance indicators** (KPI) that are used to monitor the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy as well as results to-date. This also constitutes an activity report for all the tasks of WP7 and WP8.

Section 5 is reserved for the **conclusions and a summary** of the next activities.

1.1 Portfolio of assets and results

The basis for the dissemination and exploitation plans will be the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KER). The following is a first mapping of results and grouping of KERs based on component results identified from the DoA.

- KER 1 (Academy and Awards): European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework:**
 A new institution, the EOSA, will be established that will own and take up the Awards Framework and form the basis and sustainability for the annual European Open Source Awards. This KER will include the institution itself, the awards procedure, sustainability mechanisms and the pilot academy members and network.
- KER 2 (Skills Strategy): Strategy for OS Skills Development:** This KER includes customised training modules aimed at professionals and students, as well as SMEs to close the gap between academic knowledge and real-world industrial application as well as workshops, masterclasses, and industry-led seminars designed as part of the project aiming to increase European proficiency in open source technology.
- KER 3 (OS Thought-Leadership): Thought-Leadership Outputs and Tools:** This KER includes reports, tools or methodologies produced within the project that are meant for uptake or sage by external stakeholders. This KER will position the Academy as a major resource for best practices, policy suggestions, and strategic advice in the European open-source community.

Below are the component results under each KER that have been mapped from the DoA. Further results may be identified during the course of the project. The contributors have also been tracked to provide a first identification of foreground intellectual property rights (IPR).

KER	Component Results	Contributors
KER 1: European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework	KR1.1: Critical areas to recognise and metrics for identification of potential nominees and custom awards. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D3.1 Manual on the use of OS indicators (KPI1.2.2) 	RISE
	D4.1 OS Academy Constitution	OFE
	KR2.2: Develop a comprehensive awards framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D4.2 Awards framework D5.2 Awards framework 2 	OFE
	KR2.3: Recurrent annual European OS Awards Ceremony <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D4.3 Awards Event framework 1 D5.3 Awards Event framework 2 D4.4 Post-event report: Awards Event 1 D5.4 Post-event report: Awards Event 2 	Trust-IT
	D5.1 Sustainability plan for the EU Open Source Week initiatives	OFE
	KR4.1: OSAwards.EU permanent web presence	Trust-IT
	KR4.2: Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan & Strategy (DECP) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D7.1 First Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan 1 	Trust-IT, OFE, RISE

KER	Component Results	Contributors
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D7.2 Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan 2 D8.1 Final Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Report 	
KER 2: Strategy for OS Skills Development	D6.1 Exploitation and Sustainability Guidelines and Quality Assurance	BSC
	KR3.2: Develop Lifelong Learning Programmes and Tailored OS Modules <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D6.2 Skills Strategy and Lifelong Learning Programs Grade & Master Module on OS Hardware & Software Advanced Pre-Doctoral Module on OS/OH 	BSC, RISE, Tecnalia
	D6.3 OS Skills Resource Hub and Continuous Improvement (KR3.3)	BSC
KER 3: Thought-Leadership Outputs and Tools	D3.2 OS Indicator Design and Policy Recommendations	RISE
	Policy & Technology Briefs <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI1.1.1 Policy recommendations for increased interest for the contribution to, integration of and exploitation of OS assets in Europe 3 Policy Briefs 	Tecnalia, RISE
	KR1.2 Visualisation tool of OS projects	Tecnalia

1.2 Stakeholder analysis, value proposition and messaging

A more in-depth analysis of the five stakeholders from the description of action is presented below with specific attention to priority of engagement, most relevant KERs, and messaging. Stakeholders are classified either as “Primary” - key actors for the uptake/exploitation of the result or “Secondary” - relevant, but not a key actor in the uptake/exploitation of the results.

1. Policymakers		Type: Primary
Description	Policymakers include people responsible for developing and implementing public policy. They are the single most important group for uptake of the Academy and its messaging, as the goal is to uplift open source excellence and success to drive change in society.	
Examples	EC, Member State Governments, specialised agencies	
Most relevant KERs for uptake/exploitation &	KER 1 (Academy and Awards)	“Through an established recognition system, EOSA and the OS Awards is your partner and means to encouraging the growth of OS in Europe.”

messaging	KER 3 (OS Thought-Leadership)	<i>“EOSA is an established network of European OS leaders and is a brains-trust that can be relied upon for consultations on OS policy.”</i>
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Source Awards • Direct Outreach • Campaigns and Advocacy • Mailing Lists • Thought Leadership Pieces • Policy Briefs • Blogs and Articles 	

2. Industry Players		Type: Primary
Description	Industry Players are people working in or around technology or technology-dependent industries who may be aware of open source, but are not so aware of how open source is driving impact in their fields. It is key to reach them and lift up their contributions and work through the campaign to drive change.	
Examples	Mercedes-Benz, IBM, Qualcomm	
Most relevant KERs for uptake/exploitation & messaging	KER 1 (Academy and Awards) KER 3 (OS Thought-Leadership)	<i>“Companies that harness the power of OS benefit from significant competitive advantages with world-leading home-grown (European) talent and technologies ready to be relied upon.”</i>
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Source Awards • Direct Outreach • Campaigns and Advocacy • Mailing Lists • Thought Leadership Pieces • Blogs and Articles 	

3. Open Source Players		Type: Primary
Description	Open Source Players here can be understood as organisations such as trade/business associations, think tanks, NGOs or people who work directly or indirectly on projects or issues related to open source, and who do not necessarily need to be convinced of its efficacy. They are a primary stakeholder to reach, as their support helps fulfil the main goals of the Academy. However, given their already high awareness of the value of open source, they are not the most important stakeholder group.	

Examples	Open Source Awards, Open Source Initiative, Eclipse Foundation, OW2, European Processor Initiative (EPI)	
Most relevant KERs for uptake/ exploitation & messaging	KER 1 (Academy and Awards)	<i>“European OS contributions are recognised. Be part of the network of the most impactful players in European OS.”</i>
	KER 2 (Skills Strategy)	<i>“Keep yourself at the cutting edge and benefit from the training courses available via the EOSA.”</i>
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media Channels • Mailing Lists • Podcasts and YouTube • Webinars • In-Person Events • Training Programmes 	

4. General Public		Type: Secondary
Description	Citizens are members of the everyday population that cross-cut many groups. Targeting them is a second-order of all Academy communications but should not be its main focus.	
Example Personas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press and media – tier 1 -2 	
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All Academy Communications (no need for micro-targeting) 	

5. Investors and Funding Bodies		Type: Secondary
Description	Investors and Funding Bodies are people responsible for funding or investing in the open source ecosystem, either from the public or the private sectors. Targeting them is a second-order of targeting Policymakers and Industry Players.	
Examples	EU Member State Governments, Open Source Foundations, EC	
Most relevant KERs for uptake/ exploitation & messaging	KER 3 (Thought-Leadership)	<i>“EOSA’s OS Projects Visualisation tool provides a comprehensive overview of where OS investments are heading. EOSA’s policy recommendations can also provide hints on potential OS investment gaps where funding could be directed.”</i>
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Source Awards • Direct Outreach • Mailing Lists • Thought Leadership Pieces 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blogs and Articles • Policy Briefs
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1.3 Communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives

OS Awards.EU implements a focused communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy. KERs have been identified to group the key results and outputs of the project. Each of which is backed by communication and dissemination campaigns that support exploitation. This ensures that dissemination, communication and exploitation KPIs and goals directly contribute to the achievement of the project objectives.

Project Objective	Relevant KERs	Comms & Dissemination Objectives and Measures	Exploitation/Uptake Plan
Objective 1: Create a framework for a sustainable recognition scheme for OS in Europe	KER 1: European Open Source Academy and Awards Framework	Position the Academy as a player in the European OS ecosystem. <i>(Campaign 1: Branding & Awareness)</i>	Work to ensure acceptance of the recognition framework and its legitimacy within Europe. Long-Term Institution Building: Develop a legal entity for EU OS Academy to sustain the awards or be sustained further via a funder. Project website revised into Academy website to be the institution's main online channel. RISE, APELL, BSC will utilise gathered success stories to support its own advocacies within their own communities.
Objective 2: Establish a European OS Awards Ceremony to promote OS contributions		Ensure high participation and visibility of awards events <i>(Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion & Recruitment)</i>	Explore the annual awards event series being absorbed as part of academy activities to support its sustainability. Incorporation as part of OFE's annual European OS Week. Pursue synergies with Free Open Source Software Developers' European Meeting (FOSDEM) including opportunities for inclusion as part of the programme.
Objective 3: Increase European skills in OS to build a strong workforce	KER 2: Strategy for OS Skills Development	Demonstrate high interest for the Academy upskilling outputs <i>(Campaign 2: Academy)</i>	Integration of modules into universities and industry training. Future Academy entity maintains European OS Resource Hub.

		Awareness (Participation)	& Professional Recognition: Explore possibility of an OS endorsement system BSC will endorse OS courses for its own network.
Objective 4: Increase OS engagement through awareness campaigns and synergies	KER 3: Thought Leadership Outputs and Tools	Promote OS adoption in public sector, critical industries, and SMEs via multipliers. (<i>Campaign 4: Open Source Synergies</i>)	Uptake of OS policy recommendations for national OSPOs. Incorporate OS indicators in DESI, EU Innovation Scoreboard. Fraunhofer ISI to integrate OS indicators in the portfolio of science and technology indicators produced for the German government and EC. Trust-IT to explore OSAwards.EU opportunities in OS & ICT standardisation for its own standardisation initiatives. Tecnalia and BSC to exploit technology transfer opportunities relevant to its own activities.
This is a horizontal objective which supports all KERs and their respective dissemination and exploitation plans .			

2 Approach and methodology

2.1 Resources

The OS Awards.EU communications, dissemination and exploitation activities are a joint, coordinated effort of all OS Awards.EU partners who have committed to contributing according to the effort allocated to them. Even partners that do not have effort in WP7 and 8 have agreed to provide input on communication and outreach activities.

Figure 1 WP7&8 Staff Effort (combined)

2.1.1 Roles

A communication team will be established for EOSA that will provide the backbone for the communication, dissemination, outreach activities. Supporting members will provide support via presentations at events or supporting press outreach activities.

Core Communications Team: Sarina Magham (Trust-IT); *Communications Manager*, Anja Radonjic (Trust-IT); *Events and Content Specialist*, Luca Di Fiore (Trust-IT); *Web Developer*, Lorenzo Calamai (Trust-IT); *Graphic Designer*, and Ruben Tognetti (Trust-IT); *Videographer*.

Events and Press Outreach Support: Astor Nummelin Carlberg (OFE), Nicholas Gates (OFE), Johan Linåker (RISE), Anna Eriksson (RISE), Maria Jose Lopez (Tecnalia), and Olatz Ibañez (Tecnalia).

2.1.2 Staff Efforts in Person Months and Person Days

Work Packages 7 and 8 are effectively backed by resources for staff and necessary expenses such as travel, meeting services, and dissemination efforts, promoting efficient communication of project outcomes over the project's duration. The total expenses for these work packages represent a considerable commitment to enhancing the visibility and effectiveness of the project's dissemination and engagement activities.

Partner	WP7-8 (PMs)	WP7-8 (Person Hours)	Total PMs	Total Person Hours
Trust-IT	18	2880	18	2880
RISE	2	320	2	320
OFE	4	640	4	640

TECNALIA	2	320	2	320
BSC	1	160	1	160
COMMpla	8	1280	8	1280
APELL	0	0	0	0
Fraunhofer	0	0	0	0
Total	35	5600	35	5600

Category	Work Package 7 (€)	Work Package 8 (€)	Total (€)
Travel & Subsistence	8,000	3,000	11,000
Meeting & Seminar Services	3,250	6,500	9,750
Dissemination Services	15,500	15,500	31,000
Publication Fees	4,000	4,200	8,200

2.2 Approval procedure and guidelines

An approval procedure had been set up for communications materials that WP7&8 regards to be of high importance, urgency or sensitivity. To ensure an efficient process and a central communication channel for the team, a WP7&8 mailing list has been set up, which will include at least one representative per partners that need to give their approval (RISE and OFE), appointed by their organisation as their interface for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. The partners TECNALIA, BSC, APELL and Fraunhofer have been given an observer status while RISE and OFE need to respond within one working day to the matter that has been brought to their attention. If the partners miss to respond within one working day, it will be considered tacit consent and the matter will be handled by the work package leader Trust-IT. This process ensures that all partners are continuously updated and involved with the WP7 & 8 activities.

Step	Description	Duration
1	WP7&8 sends the request of action to the designated partners OFE and RISE, the appointed person of contact will be notified and supplied with the first version of the communication material (if applicable).	0 Days
2	The appointed POC has one working day to review the material and to respond to the matter that has been flagged. Once the feedback is provided, the process is heading to the third step.	1 Day
3	The feedback (if there is any) will be implemented.	1 Day
4	If the partners miss to provide feedback within the one working day that has been agreed on prior, the WP-leader will take this as tacit consent and proceed with the suggested action.	1 Day

Figure 2 Table of Communication approval process for WP 7&8

Communication outputs that are considered minor or not sensitive will not be bound by the review process above.

3 Communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement plan

3.1 Brand identities

The European Open Source Academy (EOSA) and OS Awards.EU each have distinct brand identities, designed for clarity, adaptability, and strong visual presence across digital and print platforms. The EOSA logo, with its blue gradient, represents professionalism, trust, and the journey from knowledge to expertise, aligning with its role in education and skills development. In contrast, the OS Awards logo, featuring dark grey and gold tones, conveys prestige and celebration, reinforcing its function as a high-profile recognition platform for open source contributions. Both logos are optimised for various formats and backgrounds, ensuring readability and consistency. Detailed brand guidelines, including colour palettes and usage rules, are provided in Appendix III.

Figure 3 Logos of EOSA & the Awards

3.2 Channels

3.2.1 Website

The EOSA website (www.europeanopensource.academy) will be the primary digital channel of the OS Awards.EU project. As part of this, a sub-section will be dedicated to the Awards (www.europeanopensource.academy/awards).

The website development plan, a summary of which is seen in Figure 4, is structured as a multi-phase rollout spanning several years, with each release introducing new features, sections, and updates based on user feedback and project milestones. As in the Description of Action (DoA), **three major releases** are foreseen. The current website has undergone the **release of 1.1 stage**.

Release 1.0 and 1.1

The initial phase, **Release 1.0**, (delivered M01) laid the foundation for the website, launching essential pages such as the homepage (HP), an awards section, a contact page, and a partners page. This release was crucial in establishing a basic online presence, setting the stage for future

enhancements. The next major update, **Release 1.1** (delivery by M06), significantly expanded the website's structure and functionality by introducing several new sections and pages.

One of the most substantial additions was the **"Academy" section**, designed to serve as a hub for various educational and informational resources. This new section incorporated multiple subsections, including pages for news, events, information about the Academy itself, Open Source Weeks (a specific feature or event series within the Academy), newsletters, and a dedicated media gallery. These additions aimed to provide a richer, more engaging user experience while enhancing content accessibility and organisation. Additionally, the awards section received a major upgrade with the introduction of a dedicated gallery, making it easier for users to browse and engage with past and present award-related content.

Figure 5 reflects the structured implementation of these updates, illustrating how the website has been organised to create a seamless and intuitive navigation experience. The Academy homepage now connects users to several key pages, including **"About Us," "Get Inspired," "News & Events,"** and **"OSWeeks,"** each of which further branches into more specific subsections. For instance, the "Get Inspired" section includes webinar recordings and interviews, while "News & Events" encompasses both general news updates and event-related content. The Academy also features an overview section that provides users with essential background information and a clear understanding of its purpose. Additionally, awards-related content has been more effectively structured, ensuring a logical and efficient browsing experience.

A key **design decision in Release 1.1** was to align the awards section closely with the Academy, ensuring consistency and minimising redundancy across related pages. As a result, several awards-related pages now point directly to their Academy counterparts, ensuring users can access the same information through different entry points while maintaining a streamlined and cohesive site structure. The awards homepage features links to an **"About Us"** section, the **"2025 Edition"** of the awards, and a **"News & Events"** section, all of which seamlessly integrate with the broader Academy framework. The consistent cross-linking between the two sections enhances user experience by reducing duplication and maintaining a unified content structure.

Release 2.0

Looking ahead, future releases will continue refining and expanding the platform based on ongoing feedback and project evolution. **Release 2.0 will introduce a new "Resources and Skills Hub,"** along with updates to the awards gallery and post-event communications as well as a section showcasing the project's current and high-value **synergies**, further enhancing the website's role as a comprehensive resource.

Future Releases

Subsequent releases, including 2.1 and 3.0, will focus on implementing additional sections and pages based on insights gathered throughout the project's lifecycle. These updates will ensure that the website remain dynamic, user-friendly, and aligned with the evolving needs of its

audience. A potential major inclusion to the website for this release could be **Visualisation Tool of OS projects and communities** (scheduled for M24)

The long-term development roadmap, culminating in the final review in May 2027, reflects a strategic approach to iterative improvements, ensuring that the platform continues to grow and adapt to meet stakeholder requirements while maintaining a strong and engaging online presence.

Figure 4 Timeline of the Website Releases 2025-2027

Figure 5 Website Release 1.1 and current status of the Webpage

3.2.2 Social Media and Content Repositories

The open source community in Europe comprises of a diverse range of stakeholders, from institutions, businesses, and individuals. In order to build trust and consistent engagement with the multiple actors, OS Awards.EU project devised a **multi-faceted strategy orchestrating information, communication, and marketing activities**.

Social Media presents a pivotal component of harnessing an extensive and active community. Since the start of the project's operational work, OS Awards.EU has actively built an online presence through social media platforms: **LinkedIn, Mastodon, Bluesky, YouTube, and Zenodo**.

Through frequent and consistent interaction, namely showcasing the Academy's activities, news and updates surrounding the project, OS Awards.EU strives at creating a strong social media foundation to **raise the project's online visibility, credibility and increase awareness** about the recognition and awards framework for open source community.

As of M05, OS Awards.EU has over **1,160 followers** on social media. Through a continuous outreach to the community, and given the launch of the Inaugural European Open Source Awards, the project increased the interest in its vision and mission, which is confirmed by the raising number of page views and unique visitors collected by the in-built analytics tools.

In 2025, OS Awards.EU will continue to implement its communications activities by utilising the social media tools and sharing compelling and up-to-date content for its stakeholders. With particular interest to our stakeholders, OS Awards.EU will showcase its **participation at internal and external events**, as well as the EOSA and their public engagement, share updates in the open source regulatory, business, and technological news, and thereby amplifying its efforts and guarantee the establishment of a consolidated and engaged online community. Moreover, an engaged community are future potential attendees and nominees of the European Open Source Awards, thus ensuring credibility and garnering interests around EOSA and its Awards. In addition, the OS Awards.EU project will complement its work with **social listening** to continuously be aware of the needs and interests of the target audience and measure its efforts success in relation to KPIs.

3.2.2.1 LinkedIn

As one of the cornerstone platforms for professional developments and networking, LinkedIn enables users to connect around shared interest topics, and in the case of OS Awards.EU, spread awareness about open source to a vast audience. By publishing timely and diverse content on LinkedIn, OS Awards.EU has already started building an active online community of open source experts and non-experts, and addresses the need for quality content on European based solutions and initiatives. The channel is accessible via

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosacademy1>.

3.2.2.2 Mastodon

Mastodon operates on the basis of open source decentralised, federated servers, with each server garnering in particular the attention and engagement of specific interest groups. OS Awards.EU is presented on this platform via its channel <https://fosstodon.org/@europeanOSAcademy>, with a unique opportunity to creating tailor made content for the open source community, such as developers, open source

initiatives, and businesses. Albeit a smaller number of users, Mastodon is particularly used by specialised relevant audiences, presenting a way for meaningful engagement through concise short messages, and establishment of the EOSA as a recognisable institution amongst its peers.

3.2.2.3 Bluesky

In order to be continuously aware of the values and interests of the European open source community, and as a newly-started project, OS Awards.EU opted for the use of Bluesky over X, moving all our short-format posts and closing the previously established account. The decision was made given the deterioration of X's regulation and the increasing use of Bluesky, with its open communication protocols. In a similar format to X's micro-blogging, Bluesky allows to share concise messages and reach out to interest specific audiences. The platform is used for concise and immediate updates, a feature especially useful during events like the Inaugural Open Source Awards. The channel can be accessed via <https://bsky.app/profile/eosa.bsky.social>.

3.2.2.4 YouTube

As a method of awareness raising, the video content format is fundamental for communicating the scope and impact of the European Open Source recognition and awards framework in boosting the European technologies. OS Awards.EU will produce and publish videos on YouTube, as one of the most recognised video sharing platforms. The ultimate goal is creating and disseminating videos and interviews that spread knowledge and raise awareness about the value of open source, and how EOSA plans to amplify its importance. It can be accessed via: <https://www.youtube.com/@EuropeanOpenSourceAcademy>.

3.2.2.5 Zenodo

All public deliverables, once submitted to the EC, and research outputs will be published in Zenodo, a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. The project's channel can be found in: <https://zenodo.org/communities/osawards/>

The repository allows for the publications to be described with the appropriate metadata and can be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). The repository is harvested and items exposed via

various other research search tools. All of these are functionalities that support adherence to FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data principles and enabling open science.

3.2.3 Events

In order to establish a rapport and also build visibility with different EOSA audiences, a series of target events will be organised or attended during the course of the project with clear objectives, stakeholder audience and expected outputs in mind.

3.2.3.1 Academy events

Academy events are key to fostering collaboration and engagement within the European Open Source (OS) ecosystem. Central to this are three OS Academy Masterclass workshops/CEO roundtables, held in-person or hybrid, where EOSA members participate to showcase expertise in key aspects of Open Source Software and Hardware, in order to help the ecosystem develop awareness and understanding of excellence in those fields. Where more impactful, the OS Academy Masterclass Workshops could be turned into CEO Roundtables that would be bringing together high-level executives from major companies and SMEs to discuss issues affecting OS adoption, fostering dialogue between decision-makers and thought leaders to drive innovation and policy.

The Academy also promotes recognition and advocacy for Open Source Software and Hardware excellence, highlighting outstanding contributions through nominations and public events. Masterclasses and CEO Roundtables will showcase these achievements, encouraging further involvement in the OS movement.

Date	Proposed Topics/Focus	Target Audience
15 Jan 2025 (Delivered)	Webinar: Open Source for Responsible & Trustworthy AI: "decoding" the potential of European Open Source Community	Academics, Industry Leaders, Developers, Innovators, Policymakers
Q2 2025	Webinar: Cybersecurity and Open Source This webinar centres the discussion about the open source security, and its role in the development of trustworthy AI.	Developers, Policymakers, Industry Stakeholders
Q4 2025	Workshop: OS Academy Masterclass: Zen and the Art of Open Source Maintenance with Daniel Stenberg This masterclass offers candid insights into the routines, mental frameworks, and human realities behind sustaining open source software at scale.	Innovators, Developers Academics
Q3 2025	Webinar: Open Source and Cloud Understanding the interconnected relationship between the cloud and open source technologies.	Innovators, Researchers, Developers
Q2 2026	Workshop: OS Academy Masterclass: Building, Sustaining, and Securing Source Impact with Amandine Le Pape Security From grassroots origins to powering government-level	Industry Stakeholders, Policymakers, Developers

	infrastructures, this masterclass shows how to take an open protocol to the mainstream.	
Q3 2026	Workshop: OS Academy Masterclass: Building and Sustaining an Open Source Community Focused on practical structures and cultural dynamics, this masterclass is a playbook for cultivating strong and inclusive open source communities.	Community Managers, Developers, Academics, Industry Stakeholders
Q1 2026	Webinar: The Future of Open Hardware Exploring the potential for open hardware to revolutionise industries like manufacturing and electronics.	Engineers, Hardware Developers
Q2 2026	Webinar: Network Infrastructure Content of this webinar are still to be confirmed.	Academics, Developers, Innovators
Q3 2026	Webinar: Open Source in Industry Content of this webinar are still to be confirmed.	Policymakers, Industry Stakeholders, Developers
Q1 2027	Workshop: OS Academy Masterclass: Teaching Open Source and Open Hardware Skills with David Cuartielles For educators and open hardware tinkerers, this masterclass explores how to design hands-on learning experiences that demystify electronics and coding.	Policymakers, Public Sector Leaders, Academics, Hardware Developers

This is a preliminary event plan and may be subject to changes pending validation by the academy members.

3.2.4 Third-Party Events

OS Awards.EU partners and EOSA Academy Members will actively participate in relevant third party events (both on-site and virtual including podcasts) as speakers, panel participants, organising workshops, or presenting posters. Presence at these events will allow:

- The promotion of OS Awards.EU work to different target stakeholders;
- Collection of new contacts for database enrichment opportunities;
- Engage directly to new potential open source audiences;
- Develop synergies with different organisations and initiatives, for potential collaboration;
- Dissemination of EOSA event findings and engagement with the open source community.
- Promotion of open source

An Event Tracker allows members and consortium members to log their attendance at industry events, amplifying EOSA's visibility and ensuring key messages reach broader audiences. This tool also supports content creation for media outreach and social media campaigns, strengthening advocacy efforts. The current status of the event tracker can be found in the next chapter.

3.2.5 Email and Newsletters

One newsletter will be sent out every three months, its content will be shaped around the important EOSA developments featuring news, events, and articles published on the EOSA website. Newsletters will also include details about upcoming and past events as well as achievements and relevant messages for the EOSA community.

Aside from collecting newsletter subscribers through events, face-to-face meetings, consortium network and social media, we have also set up a sign up area for the newsletter through the website. This helps building a valued network database interested in receiving updates about the project. The collection of these contacts complies with the GDPR and the EOSA Privacy Policy. We will also consider the open-rate and click-rate of each newsletter sent, to verify the success rate of this activity.

3.2.6 Press and Media Visibility

Following the kick-off, it was clear that press and media visibility would need a stronger focus than originally foreseen in the DoA. For this reason, the first press and media engagement activities were planned to be carried out to understand better how to generate press coverage for EOSA, the Awards, the EU OS Week and the project. Press and media visibility will be generated via the following:

- **Organic coverage:** OS Awards.EU will build up the reputation of EOSA as a key player in the ecosystem worthy of being covered in press and media channels. This would be done by ensuring that well established players monitored by the press reference EOSA, the Awards and the EU OS Week in their own channels. By getting other trusted sources talking about the project, it will establish the project's reputation among the press and media. Additionally, the communications team of EOSA will ensure that the website applies search engine optimisation allowing journalists who are doing their research on open source will find EOSA and understand its role in the landscape.
- **Press Releases and their uptake:** Newsworthy occasions or story opportunities generated by the project will be identified and press releases will be drafted to be disseminated. Once a story opportunity has been identified, the communications team will identify relevant press and media channels that could potentially be interested in taking up the press release. The consortium's communication teams or press offices will also be asked to support in the dissemination of press releases. Uptake will be tracked.
- **Invitations to the press:** Similar to the previous point, flagship events of EOSA will be identified for press coverage and a list of the most relevant press and media outlets will be compiled and invited to attend. At least one month advance notification will be given to press and media in the same country while overseas journalists will be notified two to three months in advance.

Among the types of media channels that may be targeted include print and digital news and magazines, mass media, podcasts etc.

Among other potential tools and tactics to be explored once EOSA gains significant critical mass and visibility will be to organise **press conferences** and **provide travel support** for journalists representing high-visibility press and media outlets.

At present, the main stories that have been identified for potential press and media visibility are:

- The establishment of the EOSA
- The annual European Open Source Awards and winners

3.3 Implementation Planning

Our objective is to maximise visibility and engagement for the upcoming event by leveraging strategic media outreach, fostering key relationships, and utilising diverse communication channels. Based on insights gained from the inaugural awards, we recognise the importance of timely engagement with the press, making full use of our media contacts, and ensuring consistent messaging across all platforms.

To achieve this, our media outreach strategy will focus on crafting a compelling press release that highlights the event's key aspects and distributing it to relevant journalists, bloggers, and media outlets at least **four weeks in advance**. We will proactively follow up with our contacts to secure coverage, provide necessary materials such as images and quotes, and schedule interviews with key figures. Strengthening our relationships with journalists and influencers will be a priority, ensuring ongoing collaboration and increased visibility.

In addition to traditional press engagement, we will adopt a multi-channel approach to promotion. Our social media platforms, including Bluesky, LinkedIn, Mastodon and YouTube, will be instrumental in generating interest. Interactive content such as live Q&A sessions, behind-the-scenes glimpses, and short videos will help engage our audience. Collaborations with industry influencers and thought leaders will amplify our messaging, while targeted email campaigns and outreach through EOSA's network will broaden our reach.

A strong content strategy will underpin our efforts, with blog posts, infographics, and video content designed to captivate and inform our audience. Messaging consistency across all channels will be key, ensuring alignment between press materials, social media narratives, and promotional assets. Media partners will be provided with pre-written content to facilitate seamless dissemination.

On the day of the event, we will have a dedicated media area where journalists can access event information and conduct interviews. High-quality photos and videos will be captured for real-time updates, encouraging "live-tweeting" and social media engagement under an official event hashtag to maximise visibility.

Following the event, we will send thank-you notes and post-event press releases to media contacts, summarising key takeaways and media highlights. Sharing testimonials, media mentions, and event highlights across digital platforms will sustain momentum. Additionally, we will gather feedback from media representatives and attendees to refine our PR approach for future events.

3.3.1 Horizontal activities

To ensure a successful implementation of the four main communication campaigns, which are listed in section 3.3.2, several horizontal & recurring activities will be implemented and carefully monitored to ensure KPIs agreed upon in the Grant Agreement are achieved.

3.3.2 Campaigns

3.3.2.1 Campaign 1: Branding and Awareness & Recurring Activities

In order to establish the EOSA and Awards as a brand across the Open Source community, exuding prestige, several activities were devised several activities that will support the implementation of a consistent visual identity. Through a series of quarterly newsletters, weekly social media posts, community members garnered from events and post engagement, Campaign 1 will increase the recognisability of the EOSA and Awards brands within the EU and global OS ecosystem and across all target groups. Additional monitoring also involve website visitors and publication views.

3.3.2.2 Campaign 2: Academy Awareness & Participation

The scope of this campaign encapsulates the newly formed European OS Academy and their activities, including Academy Masterclass workshops, and thematic webinars. While the campaign will be implemented throughout the project, it will be divided into three phases that will each aim to increase website visits, social media followers and video views:

- Phase 1 Awareness until M10
- Phase 2 Establishment until M20
- Phase 3 Towards Sustainability until M30

As part of the campaign, the following will be carried out:

- 3 masterclasses/CEO roundtables (see academy events for planned topics and timeline).
- 4 videos: Academy presentation video, Awards & Academy members presentation video, EC on the value of open source, Resource Hub Promotional video.
- 6 webinars (see academy events for planned topics and timeline).
- 3 policy & technology briefs.

3.3.2.3 Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion & Recruitment

This campaign is dedicated to raising awareness for the annual EU OS Awards and the new EU OS Week. The promotion of the series of EOSA ceremonies aims to engage the representatives of

various entities from across the EU OS community, including foundations, industry, academia, OSPOs, policy makers, standardisation experts, and individuals. Since the event is by invitation only, the goal will not be to increase registrations but rather to build anticipation and raise the profile of the annual ceremonies establishing and positioning it as the exclusive prestigious event for the European open source community. Alongside the range of content before, during and after the European Open Source Awards, the promotion of the newly established EU OS Week, and masterclass findings will be shared as well. Key activities that will be part of the campaign include:

- Delivery of promotional banners.
- An up-to-date event website.
- Dedicated social media posts before, during and after the event.
- Production of videos: OS project presentation video, post-event video, video interviews.
- Testimonial cards showcasing participants.

3.3.2.4 Campaign 4: OS Synergies

To establish EOSA as a lighthouse of open source in Europe, Campaign 4 is essential for supporting the building of synergies with established open source communities. The Academy members will be the pivotal connectors between the Awards and the EU OS landscape, since they represent a variety of backgrounds and with deep links across the entire community. In the DoA, two KPIs were laid out for synergies, 100 and 30. To reconcile this while keeping with the spirit of the KPIs, we have defined **100 total synergies** to be established, **30 of which should be high-value synergies**.

Synergies are defined in the DoA as participation to the EOSA events. This will be the minimum criteria to recognise a synergy. In order to be counted as a high-value synergy, the collaboration between the OS Awards.eu and/or Academy and external organisation should be conscious and ongoing. A synergy would also be referred to dedicated one-on-one meeting between the project and the external organisation, with the outcome of the meeting being the support of project's achievement of KERs.

4 Monitoring

4.1 Horizontal activities

The implementation of the four campaigns is already underway, with significant progress made on the efforts to raise awareness about the European OS Academy and the Awards. On a monthly basis, we monitor various key performance indicators, such as website views, social media followers, and webinar attendees. In the table below, we highlight some of the Key Performance Indicators over the course of project start to M05. The tables do not include all KPIs currently monitored by the EOSA team.

4.1.1 Campaign 1: Branding and Awareness & Recurring Activities

Indicators	Target	Frequency	Status	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5
Social Media Posts	4	Weekly	On-track	63	39	150	87	45
Community Members	1,000	By end	Ongoing	0	0	231	231	231
Website Visitors	15,000		Needs att'n	28	103	296	409	488

Activities yet to be started are the release of publications, newsletters, and masterclasses. Once these activities have kicked off, they will appear in the next iteration of this report.

The launch of the EOSA through the first webinar on Open Source AI, as well as the Inaugural Open Source Awards have served as a significant boost to the project's visibility and as introductory events of the project's mission and vision to the open source community. We have maintained the initial attention and engagement with the audience, by publishing up-to-date news and articles in open source, showcasing the main takeaways from the Inaugural Open Source Awards, and various speaking engagements at external events of the OS Awards.EU consortium.

4.1.2 Events - Third-Party

The OS Awards.EU partners and EOSA members aim to promote the project or Open Source in general at some events, as listed in the table below. Additional events for the upcoming year can also be found. So far, **8 third-party events** have had project or academy member promotion and project visibility.

Event	Date/s	Location	OS Awards.EU/EOSA Representative & Form of Visibility
The European Open Source Policy Summit	31.01.2025	Belgium	Astor Nummelin Carlberg, Sachiko Muto (OFE) - References during event
STEAMBRACE - Future of STEAM Education Congress	03.02.2025	Sweden	David Cuartielles (EOSA) - Presentation

Congreso Nacional STEAM	08.02.2025	Spain	David Cuartielles (EOSA) - Presentation
EDGEAI conference 2025	26.02.2025	USA	David Cuartielles (EOSA) - OS Training
Mobile World Congress 2025	03.03.2025 - 06.03.2025	Spain	Anna Escoda (BSC) - Session
Hackaday Berlin	15.03.2025	Germany	David Cuartielles (EOSA) - Keynote
Workshop on TinyML for Sustainable Development	24.03.2025 - 04.04.2025	Malawi	David Cuartielles (EOSA) - OS training
Foss-north	14.04.2025 - 15.04.2025	Sweden	Daniel Stenberg (EOSA) - Speaker
UN Open Source Week	16.06.2025 - 20.06.2025	USA	Side-event planned to be organised for EOSA.
Joy of Coding	27.06.2025	Netherlands	Daniel Stenberg (EOSA) - Speaker
Wikimania	06.08.2025 - 09.08.2025	Kenya	Lydia Pintscher (EOSA) - TBC

4.1.3 Press and Media

Since the project start and until present, 22 news pieces have been identified referencing the project, EOSA and the Awards directly.

The project has generated **16 pieces of coverage** in third-party channels in at least **six media or news channels** with the rest being relevant community channels. To provide an idea of the size of the audience of each channel, their reach is given in the third column based off of publicly available data from SimilarWeb.

Overall, the majority of coverage was produced organically with up to six being generated via press releases. Coverage put EOSA and the Awards in a positive light.

#	Channel & Date	Coverage Details	Channel Reach
1	Science Business (media) 3 Dec 2024	EU debuts open source academy to convene experts and recognise excellence (press release uptake, through a paid partnership with Science Business) Launch of EOSA announced with the inaugural awards highlighted.	150.1k monthly visits
2	NGI Commons (community) 15 Jan 2025	Open Source for Responsible and Trustworthy AI (organic coverage) EOSA webinar being promoted and EOSA and awards briefly introduced.	186 monthly visitors
3	Open Technologies Organisation Greece	European Open Source Academy & Awards (press release uptake) A news piece announcing the upcoming launch of EOSA and its awards that positions Europe as a leader in open source	3.9k monthly visits

	(EELLAK) (community) 15 Jan 2025	software and hardware.	
4	TYPO3 (community) 30 Jan 2025	Meet TYPO3 at European Open Source Awards (organic coverage) Mentions the European Open Source Awards is a new initiative that honours “outstanding achievements to the Open Source community throughout Europe.”	220.7k monthly visits
5	Wikimedia (community) 30 Jan 2025	European Open Source Award for Lydia Pintscher: Recognised for her contribution to Wikidata (organic coverage) A feature on Lydia Pintscher receiving an award from EOSA which it describes as honouring “outstanding personalities in technological innovation in Europe annually.”	48k monthly visits
6	IT Brief UK (media) 31 Jan 2025	Lydia Pintscher wins European Open Source Award 2025 (organic coverage) Cites the awards and EOSA for annually acknowledging “exceptional contributions to technological innovation within Europe”.	17k monthly visits
7	Deccan Herald (media) 3 Feb 2025	Editorial: Open standards key to India-EU ties (organic coverage) EOSA cited as an example of the EU “developing and supporting open technologies” and a reason for closer alignment between EU and India.	18.4m monthly website visits
8	Science Business (media) 10 Feb 2025	EU celebrates open source excellence (press release uptake) A news article covering the Inaugural awards and official launch of the academy.	150.1k monthly visits
9	Interoperable Europe Portal (OSOR) (community)	Celebrating European excellence in open source with the European Open Source Academy & Awards (press release uptake) Promotional piece for the Inaugural awards and the academy.	No available data
10	Basque Technology Park (community) 24 Feb 2025	TECNALIA, together with other European partners, is promoting the European Open Source Academy to strengthen the continent’s digital sovereignty (press release) EOSA highlighted as an initiative that fosters the “development of knowledge, debate and inspiration to promote the use of and contributions to open source.”	3.6k monthly visits
11	Cadena Ser Bilbao (media) 4 Mar 2025	Radio Programme Feature: Hoy por Hoy Bizkaia (organic coverage) EOSA highlighted at during a local radio programme via interview with Tecnalia speakers at the Mobile World Congress.	27.1 website visits

12	UN Office of Information and Communications Technology (community) 25 Mar 2025	Sixteen Organizations Endorse the UN Open Source Principles (organic coverage) EOSA cited as one of the strategic endorses of the UN Open Source Principles	241.9k monthly visits
13	Open Culture Foundation (community) 27 Mar 2025	2025年3月開放科技新聞摘要/ Open Tech News Roundup for March 2025 (press release uptake) EOSA and awards cited as a way to recognize individuals and organisations who have made outstanding contributions to the open source community and presented as a trusted information source with statistics provided.	5.9k monthly visits
14	Linux Professional Institute (community) 31 Mar 2025	Linux Professional Institute (LPI) Endorses UN Open Source Principles (organic coverage) EOSA cited as one of the strategic endorses of the UN Open Source Principles along with LPI	188.5k monthly visits
15	Estrategia [empresarial] (media) 1 Apr 2025	Tecnalia promueve la Academia Europea Open Source (press release) EOSA highlighted as an initiative that fosters the “development of knowledge, debate and inspiration to promote the use of and contributions to open source.”	16.6k monthly visits
16	Forward Pathway (community) 6 Apr 2025	The Value of Open Source in Higher Education and Research: Cloud Adoption, Ethical Considerations, and Future Trends (organic coverage) EOSA highlighted as “another great example of a government initiative that supports open-source development. By providing resources, training, and recognition to open-source contributors, EOSA is helping to foster a vibrant and sustainable open-source ecosystem in Europe.”	46.2k monthly visits

Apart from the uptake of the press releases and organic coverage in third-party channels, channels controlled by the consortium have also been active in disseminating updates within their communities:

1. 28 Nov 2024: OFE | [European Open Source Academy & Awards: Celebrating European Excellence in Open Source](#)
2. 09 Dec 2024: Trust-IT | [The Launch of the European Open Source Academy to award excellence in open source](#)
3. 05 Feb 2025: OFE | [OpenForum Europe Celebrates Exciting Milestones at Annual EU Open Source Policy Summit](#)
4. 07 Feb 2025: Trust-IT | [Trust-IT contributing to a new era of Open Source in Europe](#)

5. 10 Feb 2025: RISE | [Europe's digital future spells open source – Now pioneers are awarded](#)
6. 13 Feb 2025: Tecnalía | [Launch of the new European Open Source Academy](#)

4.1.4 Campaigns

4.1.4.1 Campaign 2: Academy Awareness & Promotion

The table below reflects KPIs for the first phase of the second communications campaign, “Academy Phase 1 Awareness”, which will last from M01 (Nov’24) to M10 (Aug ’25).

Indicators	Target	Status	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5
Website Sessions Per month	200	Ongoing	51	126	566	814	963
Total Social Media Followers	200	Ongoing	61	128	822	1076	1266
You Tube Views	150	Ongoing	14	33	94	106	215

A range of multimedia posts were released to increase the awareness of EOSA, their structure, and how the organisation plans to boost open source into the forefront of European technological innovation. We have developed European Open Source Academy teasers ahead of the inaugural awards, speaker cards reflecting on their background and vision behind each award categories, as well as press release about the establishment of EOSA. Additionally, the website also highlights events which the Academy members will be attending or speaking at.

The first **webinar** on “[Open Source for Responsible and Trustworthy AI : "decoding" the potential of European Open Source Community](#)” was held in M3, ahead of the Inaugural Open Source Awards, which gathered **70 registered attendees**, serving as an introduction to the EOSA and the project’s vision and goals to the European open source community.

A **promotional video for EOSA** was produced which has so far garnered **100+ views**: <https://youtu.be/pMzK-Hv98uk>

Figure 6 EOSA promotional video screenshot

Two videos on Awards & Academy members presentation video and EC on the value of open source are currently being produced. The following are the next targets by M20 and M30:

	Campaign 2.2 Academy Phase 2 Establishment (by M20)	Campaign 2.3 Academy Phase 3 Towards Sustainability (by M30)
Website sessions per month	400	600

Total Social Media Followers	500	900
YouTube Views	350	600

4.1.4.2 Campaign 3: Flagship Event Promotion and Recruitment

The table below refers to activities of Inaugural Awards Ceremonies Promotion, occurring between M01 to M05.

Indicator	Target	Results	Metric
Total posts across social media	80	150	Total clicks
Event Page views	600	Ongoing	Page views
Inaugural Awards Ceremony Attendees	100	150	Attendees
Post event video delivered	1	70	Total views
Video Interviews Published	8	1	Videos

For the establishment of a distinct sense and visual identity of European Open Source Awards, the OS Awards.EU team designed and produced a variety of promotional material, from speaker banners, roll-ups, posters, pins, and the physical OS Awards. Moreover, we issued live updates during the Inaugural Awards ceremony, ensuring the audience and those interested attending in the future are familiar with the format, award categories, and the vision behind the celebration.

The **post-event video** was delivered and garnered more than **80 views** so far: <https://youtu.be/1rT5wvTlIaw>

Figure 7 Inaugural Awards Ceremony Post-Event Video screenshot

One **video testimonial** from participants has been produced so far with seven more planned: <https://youtu.be/1StbhV4xRn4>.

Figure 8 Testimonial video screenshot

4.1.4.3 Campaign 4: OS Synergies

The fourth campaign will begin its monitoring from M06, tracking the synergies established with other open source projects and initiatives in Europe. Nevertheless, introductory meetings and brainstorming sessions over areas of alignment have already begun. Some of the organisations we are looking to share content with and invite as contributors to OS Awards.EU project events or activities include Simpl Programme, EPCC, Open Source Initiative, Next Cloud, and the Linux Foundation. The following are the results of the campaign to-date.

Indicators	Target	Status	M6 (Apr '25)
Total synergies established	100	To start	126
- Of which, 30+ are high-value synergies	30	To start	5
Synergies webpage views by M15	150	To start	0

Further information on the high-value synergies are provided below:

Organisation	Date	Contact Role	Notes
Sovereign Tech Agency	02.02.2025	Head of Sovereign Tech Fund	Had an interview and will be establishing a contact once the interview has been finalised.
Open Source Initiative	05.02.2025	Head of Community	1-on-1 meeting along with RISE and OFE. Comms synergy established. Ceremony promoted in their 15k outreach newsletter, further collaboration possibilities have been discussed, like a community blog.
Open Source Initiative	10.02.2025	Policy Advocate	Comms synergy: one hour interview for a blog post after that we also remained in contact for synergy purposes.
Simpl Programme	20.02.2025	IT Project Officer	1-on-1 meeting to explore possible joint workshops, integration in webinars and perhaps exploring on site event possibilities or promoting each other.
Nextcloud	04.04.2025	CEO	Comms synergy: Had an interview for a blogpost.
UN	06.04.2025	Open Source Coordinator	Engagement request for the Academy

5 Conclusions

The delivery of D7.1 First Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan provides an overview of the planned activities under the scope of WP7-8 and provides a direction for the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities at this early stage of the project.

The report establishes the logical relationship between the project results, how they are expected to be taken up and exploited in the future and what communication and dissemination activities would best support them.

The report also provides the best chance for any deviations to be addressed through the strict monitoring procedures set up to track the implementation of the plan.

The next iterations, D7.2 - Intermediate Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan 2 and Deliverable D8.1 - Final Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Report will be delivered respectively in M18 (Apr'26) and M30 (Apr'27). The monitoring section will provide progress updates on the implementation of the plan.

In the upcoming iteration of the Deliverable 7.2, the monitoring section will reflect the recommendations from the newly developed Style Guide, which serves as the roadmap of sustainability for the European Open Source Academy. The Style Guide, developed by the project partners tasked with the Academy establishment, provides a set of clear guidelines on communication, conduct, and vision regarding the Academy.

Style Guide is currently under review and is not publicly available.

Explore the project and stay tuned for updates.

Communication Channels	Links
Website	https://europeanopensource.academy/
LinkedIn	European Open Source Academy
Mastodon	European Open Source Academy
BlueSky	@eosa.bsky.social

Appendix I. Handbook

The handbook is meant to be a live resource, periodically updated, to provide an easy point of reference for the communication and outreach guidelines and reference plans for the OSAwards.EU consortium. The file is accessible here:

<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/XLqTgo9t7Pqi3T2>

The current text as of 11 April 2025 can be found below.

Handbook on Communications and Outreach

This document is meant to be a live resource, periodically updated, to provide an easy point of reference for the communication and outreach guidelines and reference plans for the OSAwards.EU consortium.

Last update: 11 April 2025

Regular Calls & Meeting Minutes

- **WP7-8 and Comms Calls:** These occur on a bi-weekly basis on Thursdays, 11-12:00 CET to align on dissemination, exploitation, and communication efforts.
- Meeting minutes and schedules are documented and accessible here: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/25079>. Partners are encouraged to review them before calls.
- Attendance is expected for at least one representative from each partner organisation: TECNALIA, BSC, APELL and Fraunhofer are accepted to only attend when needed or desired.

Branding & Communication Assets

- **Branding Guidelines:** Follow project-wide branding for consistency across all materials. Access the latest guidelines here: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29180>
- **Templates & Design Assets:** Download templates for presentations, social media, and official documents here: <https://cloud.apell.info/s/79sNeSi5cn4JDtE>
- **Communication Kit:** Includes design files for rollups, general Academy presentation, flyers, posters, and digital banners. Available here: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29188>
- **Style guide:** a style guide is being developed to further harmonise the style of communication for EOSA. This file will be shared once a first version has been crystalised.

Event Participation & Support Requests

- **Notifying the Team:** Partners attending conferences, workshops, or industry events should inform the communications team at least **4 weeks in advance or alternatively update the Event tracker:** <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29188>
- **Support Available:** We provide materials, branding advice, and strategic communications support. If needed, partners can request:
 - o Co-branded materials (flyers, presentations, etc.).
 - o Social media promotion before, during, and after the event.
 - o [Press releases](#) or blog posts related to the event.

- **Collaboration Example:** For MWC, we worked with BSC to maximise visibility. Partners should refer to this case for best practices.
- Submit event details via Tracker: <https://cloud.apell.info/f/29188> or email a.radonjic@trust-itservices.com and s.magham@trust-itservices.com.

Sharing News & Updates

- **When to Share:** Partners should inform the communications team about:
 - o Submission of key deliverables.
 - o Progress on technical developments.
 - o Participation in major events or collaborations.
 - o Any other newsworthy updates.
- **How to Share:** Provide a short summary (who, what, when, where, why) via **E-Mail** to a.radonjic@trust-itservices.com or email.
- The **Academy events** and news are collected through a form provided by OFE (Nicholas Gates)
- **Amplification:** The team will coordinate dissemination through social media, newsletters, and website updates.

Key Information for Partners

- **Communications Plan (D7.1):** The full dissemination and communication plan is detailed in D7.1. Access it here. <https://cloud.apell.info/f/21308>
- **Consistency Across Channels:** Ensure messaging aligns with the overall project strategy and the neutral political stance and tone of the Academy.
- **Social Media & Website Contributions:** Partners can contribute to blog posts, case studies, and social media campaigns. Contact the communications team for guidelines.
- **Contacts & Support:** For any questions, reach out to s.magham@trust-itservices.com and a.radonjic@trust-itservices.com.

Appendix II. Style Guide

The document is meant to be a living document, continuously being updated based on the ongoing implementation of the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan. The following is the current version of the Style Guide as of 24 April 2024.

Style Guide

Last update: 24 April 2025

1. Introduction

Purpose in Context of the Communications Strategy

This style guide establishes the principles for all communications related to the European Open Source Academy (EOSA) and the annual European Open Source Awards. The guide ensures consistency, professionalism, and alignment with the overarching goal: achieving public recognition and appreciation of open source.

This means that the ultimate audience of the project as a whole is the public. But that does not mean that the direct communications by the project's team targets the public. We want to use the Academy and its members as the vehicle of communications. The overarching goal, for example, would be to get the winners of the Awards and members of the Academy to be interviewed in media with a broad reach. Our work is to create something that is worth communicating about.

The project's communications team focuses on elevating the members, their status and the exclusiveness of the Awards. Audience here is the open source community, and we want our institutions to be **different from standard open source activities**.

Scope

The guide applies to all external and internal project communications, including social media, press releases, event materials, website content, and correspondence. It also informs Academy-internal communications, such as emails from the project consortium to the Academy members.

2. Core Communication Principles

- **Gravitas:** Communications must reflect substance, weight, and dignity.
- **Excellence:** The focus is on celebrating outstanding contributions rather than broad inclusivity.
- **Formality:** A formal tone is used in all communications.
- **Selectivity:** Social media is used sparingly and strategically.
- **Neutrality:** Political commentary is avoided unless absolutely necessary.

- **Consistency:** Messaging is visually and stylistically coherent, recognisable and easy to identify across all channels.

3. Branding and Visual Identity

See full brand guide here: <https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/QHZSgRAQtmmzc4S>

Logo Usage: The OS Awards logo is used exclusively for communications related to the Awards Ceremony. All other communications must use the European Open Source Academy branding. The logo is not used excessively. Instead, the usage radiates confidence and sophistication, giving prominence for the branding with whitespace and modest sizing.

Consistent Branding: Colours, fonts, and design elements should align with the Academy's identity to ensure a cohesive presentation.

4. Language and Style Guidelines

- **No emojis** in any communication.
- **No contractions** (e.g., "cannot" instead of "can't").
- **Consistent terminology:** "Open source" should never be hyphenated.
- **Precise wording:** Avoid unnecessary embellishments or colloquialisms.
- **European English** spelling and conventions are used throughout.

5. Visual and Event Presentation

Events and Invitations

- The annual awards ceremony should be hosted in venues over 100 years old to reflect tradition and prestige.
- Consideration will be given to sending physical invitations to maintain exclusivity.
- Formal attire is required for all EOSA and Awards events.

6. Academy Protocol and Internal Communications

- **Decorum and Professional Conduct:** Academy Chairs and Members are expected to adhere to best practices in professional behaviour.
- **Titles in Communication:** Academy Chairs and Members are to be referred to as Esteemed Chairs or Esteemed Members in speech and writing during all Academy-organised communications, events and meetings.
- **Dress Code Exemption:** Academy Members are exempt from the formal dress code at Academy-organised events.
- **External Alignment:** The principles guiding internal communications should inform how the Academy communicates externally, ensuring consistency in tone and presentation.

7. Social Media and Public Relations

- **No social media takeovers.**
- **Controlled engagement:** Social media is used purposefully to maintain credibility.
- **PR Focus:** The annual main award recipient is the centre of media efforts.
- **Strategic Messaging:** Messages should highlight impact, innovation, and European leadership in open source.
- **Less is more:** well crafted, meaningful messaging instead of fillers and flooding.

8. Awards and Recognition Strategy

- **Main Award:** A singular, prestigious award is given annually to an individual.
- **Special Recognition Awards:** 4-5 awards celebrate contributions in specific categories (Community & Project, Business, Knowledge & Advocacy).
- **Sustainability of Recognition:** Special Recognition recipients may be considered for the main award in subsequent years.

9. Communications Governance

- **Approval Process:** All official communications must undergo review to ensure alignment with the style guide.
- **Consistency Check:** Regular audits of communication channels to maintain uniformity.
- **Spokesperson Protocol:** Only designated representatives may speak on behalf of the Academy and Awards.

Mood Board and Examples

The Swedish Royal Court and the structure of their website click on images to discover their website.

Written Communications - Example

News Section: <https://www.royal.uk/news-and-activity/2025-04-07/the-king-celebrates-community-music-at-a-special-reception>

Social Media Post - Example

To be provided in the next iteration.

Awards Venue - Example

To be provided in the next iteration.

Appendix III. Branding Guidelines

The branding guidelines can be found in the following link:

<https://b2drop.eudat.eu/s/QHZSgRAQtmmzc4S>

The following pages showcases the latest version of the branding guidelines.